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Decontamination of 2-Chloro ethyl ethyl sulfide using the novel TiO₂/ZnFe₂O₄/ZSM-5 nanocomposite adsorbent

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Abstract

This research examined sonocatalytic degradation of methylene blue (MB) dye in the presence of TiO₂/ZnFe₂O₄/ZSM-5 nanocomposite synthesized using the ultrasound assisted-hydrothermal route. Multiple identification techniques were utilized to investigate the TiO₂/ZnFe₂O₄/ZSM-5 nanocomposite sonocatalyst involving FESEM, EDAX, FTIR, XRD and BET. The influences of various parameters like contact time, pH, initial MB concentration and sonocatalyst dosage were precisely studied. About 98.1% of MB dye degradation was achieved under the optimum parameter conditions i.e. at pH of 7, 25 mg/L of initial MB concentration and 0.5 g/L of TiO₂/ZnFe₂O₄/ZSM-5 dosage within 60 min. The enhancement of sonocatalytic activities can be related to the function of NaY zeolite as trap state for the electron. The scavenger tests outcomes demonstrated that the sono-generated hydroxyl radical ($\cdot\text{OH}$) would play an important role in the MB degradation. Additionally, the TiO₂/ZnFe₂O₄/ZSM-5 was quite stable since the efficiency of MB degradation gained in the four run was 93.7%.

Keywords: sonocatalytic, degradation, methylene blue, TiO₂/ZnFe₂O₄/ZSM-5, nanocomposite.

Conclusion

To sum up, TiO₂/ZnFe₂O₄/ZSM-5 was successfully synthesized by the ultrasound assisted-hydrothermal method. The results revealed that the sonocatalytic degradation of MB was obviously affected by contact time, pH, initial MB concentration and sonocatalyst dosage. The highest 60 min at a pH of 7, 25 mg/L of initial MB concentration and 0.5 g/L of TiO₂/ZnFe₂O₄/ZSM-5 dosage. The sonocatalytic process applying the TiO₂/ZnFe₂O₄/ZSM-5 H₂O₂ displayed great potential in treatment of MB. In addition, TiO₂/ZnFe₂O₄/ZSM-5 could be applicable to the practical application since it showed high stability and recyclability. By this test, TiO₂/ZnFe₂O₄/ZSM-5 nanocomposite illustrates a promising candidate for the sonocatalytic degradation in environmental remediation.

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